

The Influence of Consumer Behavior and Marketing Mix Based on Digital Marketing on Purchasing Decisions (Case Study of Shabby Pink Store Consumers in Medan City)

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine "The Influence of Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing on Purchasing Decisions (Case Study on Shabby Pink Store consumers in Medan City)". Consumer behavior is defined as the dynamics of interaction between influence and awareness of behavior and the environment where humans exchange aspects of life and purchase decisions are actions taken by consumers who want to choose to buy one or more alternative products. This research uses a type of associative quantitative research. The samples in this study are respondents who have purchased products at the Shabby Pink store with a total sample of 103 respondents using a non-prob sampling technique. Sampling ability with purposive sampling approach and consumer criteria must buy at least 2x at the shabby pink store. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires via Google Forms. Based on the results of the T-test it was found that Tiktok Affiliate Marketing Promotion had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. In the Coefficient of Determination Test (R²), it can be seen that the Adjusted R Square value obtained is 0.753 (75.3%). This shows that the independent variable has a high ability to explain variations in the dependent variable (Purchase Decision) in this study. The remaining 24.7% will be affected by other factors that cannot be explained in this study.

INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of its development, the online buying and selling system was known as e-commerce, which stands for electronic commerce. According to Adi Sulisty (2016: 8), in general, e-commerce is a trade transaction through electronic media connected to the Internet. This refers to the internet network for online shopping and its reach is narrower, and the transaction method is through digital transfer. Electronic commerce or e-commerce is an activity related to the sale, marketing, purchase and payment of products or services that utilize electronic systems such as the Internet or computer networks. The emergence of the internet has changed humans in the way they transact and communicate. The ease of accessing the internet has a direct impact on the growth of social media use. This is proven by the very rapid growth of e-commerce and it is predicted that it will continue to increase in line with the increase in micro, small and medium enterprises in Indonesia. According to Bukhari Alma (2016: 96) believes that purchasing decisions are consumer decisions that are influenced financially, by technology, politics, culture, products, price, place, advertising, physical, evidence, people, and processes. To form consumer attitudes, process all information and conclude in the form of the right answer.

Consumer behavior is defined as the way consumers spend their limited resources, for example, money, time and energy to obtain the goods or services they want for satisfaction. Digital Marketing is a part of the internet, namely a medium that allows people to interact with each other without being limited by space and time. In the beginning, social media was intended as a space or place for communication and information, as the times progressed, social media took on many roles in everyday life, from things that were positive to something useful to something beneficial to something evil. One of the social media that is popular and most used by Indonesians is Instagram. In developing its business, the Shabby Pink online shop utilizes and uses Instagram social media to market and sell its products.

The digital marketing of the online shop Shabby Pink Store has not been able to encourage consumers to decide to buy its products. Apart from that, competition is getting tighter in the field of women's clothing products which allows consumers to have many alternative product choices to buy similar products to competitors. This will have an impact on consumer purchasing decisions. It is hoped that consumers will be able to buy Shabby Pink Store products even though there are many similar products on the market and the other hand, Shabby Pink Store can strengthen digital marketing and consumer behavior.

This research aims to determine and explain the influence of consumer behavior on purchasing decisions. Explain the influence of a digital marketing-based marketing mix on purchasing decisions. The influence of consumer behavior and digital marketing-based marketing mix on purchasing decisions. It is hoped that this research can increase our understanding and knowledge about the impact of consumer behavior and digital marketing-based marketing

mix on purchasing decisions and become a reference and additional information for further research.

Figure 1. Instagram ShabbyPinkStore

Shabby Pink Store is a business that operates in the fashion sector, especially offering clothing products for women. Shabby Pink Store is also inseparable from sharp competition because many companies produce similar products. Many factors can influence consumer behavior in deciding to buy a product. One of them is social media. The impact of social media varies, but what generally happens is that information and communication originating from social media will influence purchasing decisions that consumers will consider. The shabby pink store online shop uses social media in the form of Instagram as one of its marketing media.

Based on the results of observations, researchers found that several consumers purchased fashion products repeatedly because of the latest trends or models. This is reinforced by an interview with one of the consumers, namely Liya Murtina, who stated that she often buys products at Shabbypinkstore because the prices offered tend to be cheaper, so there is a desire to always buy these products even though she doesn't need them.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchase Decision

According to Kotler and Keller (2016: 194), consumer purchasing decisions are part of consumer behavior that is studied by how individuals, groups and organizations choose, buy and use goods, services, ideas or experiences that fulfill their needs and desires. Purchasing decision numbers cannot be separated from consumer behavior. Therefore, each consumer has different shopping habits. There are 5 purchasing decision processes Kotler & Armstrong, (2014) as follows:

1. *Problem recognition*. The purchasing process begins when a buyer identifies a problem or need caused by internal or external factors.
2. *Information search*. Consumers often seek a limited amount of information. The lower state of search is called keen attention.

3. *Evaluate alternatives.* Some basic concepts that help understand the evaluation process. First, consumers try to satisfy a need. Second, consumers are looking for specific benefits from product solutions.
4. *Purchase decision.* In the evaluation stage, consumers form preferences between brands in a choice set. Consumers may also form intentions to purchase the most preferred brand while personal sources exercise legitimacy or evaluation.
5. *Post-purchase behavior.* After purchase, consumers may experience conflict due to seeing certain concerning features or hearing favorable things about other brands and being wary of information that supports their decision.

Purchase Decision Indicators

Purchasing decision indicators according to Kotler and Armstrong (2016: 188) suggest that purchasing decisions have the following dimensions:

1. *Product choice.* In this case, the company must focus its attention on the people who are interested in buying a product and the alternatives they are considering.
2. *Pilihan merek.* Konsumen harus mengambil keputusan tentang merek mana yang akan dibeli setiap merek memiliki perbedaan tersendiri. Dalam hal ini perusahaan harus mengetahui bagaimana konsumen memilih sebuah merek.
3. *Choice of dealer.* Each consumer is different in terms of choosing a dealer, this could be due to close location, low prices, complete inventory, convenience in shopping, and space.
4. *Time of purchase.* Consumer decisions in choosing when to buy can vary, for example, some buy every day, once a week, once every two weeks.
5. *Purchase amount.* In this case, the company has to assemble a large number of products according to different demands.
6. *Payment method.* Consumers can choose payment methods when deciding to use products and services. Currently, purchasing decisions are not influenced by anyone.

Consumer behavior

Engel et al in Sopiah and Sangadji (2013:7), consumer behavior is the actions directly involved in the acquisition, consumption and consumption of products or services, including the processes that precede and follow these actions. According to Sunyoto (2015: 251), consumer behavior can be defined as the activities of individuals who are directly involved in obtaining and using goods or services, including the decision-making process in preparation for determining these activities.

Consumer Behavior Indicators

According to Kotler (2018), consumer behavior indicators are as follows:

1. *Cognitive component.* The object in question is the product attribute, the more positive the trust in a brand or product, the overall cognitive component will support the overall attitude emphasizing that cognitive as a form of trust will be formed through knowledge,
2. *Affective component.* Affective also reflects motivation in which a person will experience emotional dan physiological drives. In impulse

purchases, strong (affective) feelings will be followed by purchasing actions

3. *Konatifn component*. The conative component is the desire to behave (behavioral intention), so the visitor action variable in this research can be measured by indicators of the products that consumers want or choose.

Digital Marketing

According to Purwana, Rahmi, & Aditya (2017), digital marketing is an activity where sellers use cyberspace to promote their products. The world of the internet is also now able to connect with other people all over the world. Digital marketing provides a platform that simplifies relationships between producers, agents and potential buyers.

Digital Marketing Indicators

Digital marketing indicators according to Arifuddin, Kadir, & Kadir (2019) are:

1. Accessibility (accessibility)
2. Interactivity (interactivity)
3. Entertainment (entertainment)
4. Credibility (trust)
5. Irritation (irritation)
6. Informativeness (informative)

2.1 Conceptual Framework

A purchasing decision is an action taken by a consumer after going through various consideration and reference processes to choose a particular product or service that they like. Good research methods rely on research problems and objectives to achieve systematic research results. Within the framework of thinking regarding the influence of consumer behavior and digital-based marketing mix on purchasing decisions (Case Study of Shabby Pink Store Consumers on Instagram). Variables influence consumer behavior (X1), digital marketing (X2), and purchasing decisions (Y).

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

Information: X1: Influence of Consumer Behavior

X2: Digital Marketing

Y: Purchase Decision

METHODOLOGY

Types of research

The research method described in this research uses a quantitative survey method. According to Sanusi (2017: 105), a survey is a research method that uses questionnaires as a tool for combining data. To obtain information about several respondents who are interpreted to represent a certain population. According to Sugiyono (2018; 13), quantitative data is a research method based on positivistic (concrete data), research data in the form of numbers that will be measured using statistics as a calculation test tool, related to the problem being studied to produce a conclusion. Based on the questions and research objectives set out in Chapter 1, this type of research is explanatory research. Explanatory research or descriptive research is research that aims to explain a hypothesis. This study explains the influence of consumer behavior (X1), and digital marketing-based marketing mix (X2) on purchasing decisions (Y). The location of this research was carried out in Medan City among Shabby Pink Store consumers by distributing questionnaires to the respondents they wanted to target. The time of this research was carried out from April 2023 until the completion of this research report.

Research Population and Sample

Population and sample are closely related to hypotheses because statistical testing is always related to groups of subjects, such as humans, phenomena, test results, products or events. The entire group that will be studied, where the research results will be generalized, is called the population. The characteristics of the sample selected in this study are:

1. Respondents have purchased products at the Shabby Pink Store at least twice

2. Respondents aged ≥ 13 years where respondents at that age are considered adults so they can make purchasing decisions.

The following is the formula used to calculate the sample size.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Information: n: Number of samples

N: Total population

e: The percentage of inaccuracy due to sampling error that can still be desired is around 10%.

Types of Data and Data Collection Techniques

The data used in this research are primary and secondary. The data collection method that researchers used in this research was distributing questionnaires to respondents who purchased products at the Shabby Pink Store at least twice. A questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of written questions to respondents to answer Sugiyono (2017: 142). Distribution of this questionnaire is carried out online and offline via Google Forms.

RESULTS

Shabby Pink Store is a women's clothing store in the city of Medan. The Shabby Pink Store provides more than 800 products that you can choose from. Starting from pajamas or nightgowns, and regular t-shirts to jumbo t-shirts, sweaters, and various other women's clothing. The prices of clothes in this shop are very affordable, many products start at just tens of thousands. Even though it is cheap, the quality of the product is still maintained. This is proven by the high rating that the Shabby Pink Store has, namely a rating of 4.6 from 300 thousand buyer reviews. There is no reason to miss this one shop. Super complete for women's fashion issues. Even though it is a shop that is not big enough, this shop has very good service. Fast response when we chat to ask questions about the product.

Technical Data Analysis

1. Instrument Test

a. Validity test

The results of this validity test are used to see how accurate and suitable a measuring instrument is in carrying out its measuring function on a research object. Then the question item will be said to be valid if the instrument can be seen through the rcount and rtable columns. In the validity test, the researcher distributed questionnaires and gave them to 30 respondents outside the sample to find out whether the statement items were suitable for use as instruments in this research. It is generally known that the minimum requirements for a validity test will be considered to meet the requirements if $r \text{ table} = 0.361$ with $r \text{ table}$ using $df = n-2$, namely $30-2 = 28$, so that if the calculated r-value is > 0.361 then each statement item is declared valid and vice versa.

Table 1. Validity Test Estimates

Variable	Statement Items	R _{count}	r _{table}	Information
Consumer behavior (X1)	X1.1	0,832	0,361	Valid
	X1.2	0,757		Valid
	X1.3	0,763		Valid
Digital Marketing (X2)	X2.1	0,612	0,361	Valid
	X2.2	0,864		Valid
	X2.3	0,605		Valid
	X2.4	0,901		Valid
	X2.5	0,612		Valid
	X2.6	0,612		Valid
Buying decision (Y)	Y1.1	0,675	0,361	Valid
	Y1.2	0,742		Valid
	Y1.3	0,683		Valid
	Y1.4	0,678		Valid
	Y1.5	0,789		Valid
	Y1.6	0,791		Valid

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Based on the data displayed in Table 1.1, it can be concluded that all of the questions are valid and suitable for use as instruments in this research.

b. Reliability Test

Furthermore, after knowing that each instrument item was declared valid, a reliability test was then carried out using the Cronbach alpha technique which aims to compare the values in the research. There are 5 scale grouping classes with the same range, so the Cronbach alpha measure can be expressed as follows:

Table 2. Cronbach Alpha Measure Criteria

Criteria	Information
0,00 s/d 0,20	Less Reliable
0,21 s/d 0,40	Algalk Relialbel
0,41 s/d 0,60	Reliable enough
0,61 s/d 0,80	Reliablebel

0,81 s/d 1,00	Salngalt Relialbel
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The following is a presentation of the reliability values for variables X1 (Consumer Behavior), X2 (Digital Marketing) and Y (Purchase Decision) as follows:

Table 3. Variable Reliability Test Results

Variable	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Alpha Value</i>	Information
Behavior Consumer (X1)	0,803	0,81 s/d 1.00	Sangat Reliabel
<i>Digital Marketing (X2)</i>	0,787	0,61 s/d 0,80	Reliabel
Buying Decision (Y)	0,800	0,81 s/d 1.00	Sangat Reliabel

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

In Table 1.3 above, it can be seen that variable X1 (Consumer Behavior) is stated as "Very Reliable", So it can be concluded that each statement in the questionnaire is suitable for use as an instrument in this research.

2. Classic Assumption Test

Before carrying out a hypothesis test, a researcher must carry out a classical assumption test first because the classical assumption test functions to find out whether the measuring instrument used by the researcher is an effective test or not.

a. Normality test

In this research, the normality test was carried out using regression calculations through several approaches, namely the Normality Test, histogram graphic analysis, and Probability Plot graphic analysis with comparisons between several observations with different distributions that are close to a normal distribution.

a. Histogram Graphic Analysis

To see whether the data is normally distributed in the histogram graph analysis, you can see the bell-shaped histogram graph and if the graph shows to the right or left, it can be interpreted that the data is not distributed normally.

Figure 3. Histogram Graph Analysis
Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Based on the test results of the histogram graph in the image above, it is known that the data is declared normal, this can be seen from the shape of the histogram which is bell-shaped and there is no visible deviation to the right or left.

b. Probability Plot Graph

In the probability plot graph, several provisions are used to indicate whether the data will be declared normal or abnormal, namely as follows: If the results of the probability plot graph data spread around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line, then the regression model is declared normal. If the results of the probability plot graph data spread far from the diagonal and do not follow the direction of the diagonal line, then the regression model is declared abnormal.

Figure 4. Regression Standardized Residual
Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Based on the test results of the Probability Plot graph in the image above, it is known that the data is declared normal, this can be seen from the Probability Plot curve which has a distribution pattern that spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line.

b. Multicollinearity Test

To detect whether there are correlation symptoms in this study, a multicollinearity test was used. It is important to test multicollinearity in a study because of the assumption that the independent variables must be limited to the symptoms of multicollinearity. To detect symptoms of multicollinearity, you can see them by:

1. If $VIF > 10$ and tolerance value < 0.1 , it can be interpreted as multicollinearity.
2. If $VIF < 10$ and tolerance value > 0.1 it can be interpreted that multicollinearity does not occur.

So, the results of the multicollinearity test in this study can be seen in the table below:

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	5,648	2,711		2,084,040		
1	Behavior Consument	,673	,104	,576	6,461,000	,317	3,154
2	Digital Marketing	,313	,084	,331	3,713,000	,317	3,154

a. Dependent Variabel: Buying Decision

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Based on Table 1.4 it can be concluded that:

1. The VIF value of X1 (Consumer Behavior) and X2 (Digital Marketing) is 3.154 or < 10
2. Tolerance value X1 (Consumer Behavior) and X2 (Digital Marketing) is 0.317 or > 0.1

So, it can be interpreted that it is free from multicollinearity so that the regression model can be said to be reliable as a basis for analysis.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

In the heteroscedasticity test, researchers use the Glejser test because it is considered one of the most accurate ways to find out whether or not there is a similarity between the variances of the residual values in all observations of the regression model. If the Sig value. > 0.05 , it can be said that the residual variance is free from the heteroscedasticity test.

So, the results of the Glejser Heteroscedasticity test in this research can be seen in the table below:

Table 5. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Coefficients ^a				
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.

		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1.228	1.573		.781	.437
	Behavior Consument	-,041	,061	-,119	-,662	,510
	Digital Marketing	,070	,049	,254	1.409	,162

a. Dependent Variabel: Abs_Res

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Based on table 1.5, it can be concluded that the residual variance is free from heteroscedasticity, because it can be seen that the Sig. of variable X from the two variables, namely variable X1 (Consumer Behavior) of 0.510 and

4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

This model is used to determine whether there is an influence between the independent variables Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing on the dependent variable Y (Purchase Decision). The results of data management using SPSS 25.00 are as follows:

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.548	2.711		2.084	.040
	Behavior Consument	.673	.104	.576	6.461	.000
	Digital Marketing	.313	.084	.331	3.713	.000

a. Dependent Variabel: Buying Decision

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Coefficients regresi obtained:

$$Y = \alpha + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \varepsilon$$

$$Y = 5,548 + 0,673X_1 + 0,313X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Based on the multiple regression equation, it can be explained as follows:

1. The positive constant (α) is obtained with a value of 5.548, this shows that the independent variables X1 (Consumer Behavior) and X2 (Digital Marketing) have a positive effect.
2. The coefficient X1(b_1) obtained a value of 0.673, this shows that the independent variable X1 (Consumer Behavior) has a positive effect on variable Y (Purchasing Decision).
3. The coefficient X2(b_2) obtained a value of 0.313, this shows that the independent variable X2 (Digital marketing) has a positive effect on variable Y (Purchasing Decision).

5. Hypothesis Testing

a. Partial Test (T Test)

A Partial Test (T-Test) was carried out to test a partial influence between the independent variables X1 (Information), $\alpha = 0.05$).

Where:

1. If $t_{count} > t_{table} = H_0$ is rejected and H_a is accepted

2. If $t_{count} < t_{table} = H_0$ is accepted and H_a is rejected

Significance level (α) = 5% with degree of error (df) = (n-k)

N = 103

K = 3

$T_{table} = 1,984$

The hypothesis proposed in this research is "The Influence of Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing-Based Mic Marketing on Purchasing Decisions (Case Study of Shabby Pink Store Consumers in Medan City).

Table 7. Partial Test (T -Test)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.648	2.711		2.084	.040
	Behavior Consument	.673	.104	.576	6.461	.000
	Digital Marketing	.313	.084	.331	3.713	.000

Dependent: Buying_Decision

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Based on the results of the partial test (t-test) presented in Table 1.7 above, it can be concluded that:

a. Independent Variable X1 (Consumer Behavior)

In the X1 (Consumer Behavior) test, the value of count was found to be 6.461, so it is known that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table} 1.985$ and the p-value in the sig column is $0.000 < 0.05$, which means it has a significant effect. So, it can be stated that H_a is accepted, so it can be interpreted that consumer behavior has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions at the Shabby Pink Store in Medan City.

b. Independent Variable X2 (Digital Marketing)

In testing it can be stated that H_a is accepted, so it can be interpreted that Digital Marketing has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions at the Shabby Pink Store in Medan City.

c. By existing theory, it can be seen that the two variables, namely the independent variables X1 (Consumer Behavior) and X2 (Digital Marketing) have a positive and significant effect on the dependent variable Y (Purchase Decision) at the Shabby Pink Store in Medan City.

b. Simultaneous Test (F-Test)

A simultaneous Test (F-test) is carried out to determine whether the independent variables X1 (Information) and X2 (Service) contained in the

model have a joint influence on the dependent variable Y (Intention to Use).
Where:

1. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$, then it can be stated that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted.
2. If $F_{count} < F_{table}$, then it can be stated that H_0 is accepted and H_a is rejected.

Significance level (α) = 5%

Df1 (Numerator) = $k-1 = 3-1 = 2$, Df2 (Denominator) = $n-k = 103-2 = 101$

So, $F_{table} = 3.0$

Table 8. Simultaneous Test (F-Test) ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4543,447	2	2271,724	150.083	.000 ^b
	Residual	1453.098	96	15.136		
	Total	5996,545	98			

Dependent variabel: Buying_Decision

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Testing Table 1.8 shows that the value of F_{count} (150,083) $>$ F_{table} (3.09) and Sig. amounting to $0.000 < 0.05$, by existing theory, this shows that H_a is accepted, so it can be interpreted that Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions at Shabbypinkstore in Medan City.

c. Coefficient of Determination Test (R²)

The results of the Coefficient of Determination Test (R²) can be seen in table 9.

Table 9. Coefficient of Determination Test (R²) Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.870 ^a	.758	.753	3.891

Predictor variables: Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing

Source: SPSS Management Results (2023)

Based on the calculation of the Determination Coefficient Test (R²) above, it can be seen that the Adjusted RSquare value obtained is 0.753 (75.3%). This shows that the value of the independent variable Y (Purchasing Decision) which can be explained by the independent variable X1 (Consumer Behavior) and Variable X2 (Digital Marketing) is 75.3%. The remaining 24.7% will be influenced by other factors that cannot be explained in this study.

DISCUSSION

Through the results of research that has previously been tested, it was found that the results of each instrument data that had been answered by each respondent were then used to measure the independent variables X1 (Consumer Behavior) and X2 (Digital Marketing) against the independent variable Y (Purchase Decision) where the data results show that the variable is

valid and reliable. So that each indicator and statement item in this research can be reused in the future. The formulation of statements and hypotheses in this research has been answered and the results are known as follows:

a. The Influence of Consumer Behavior on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, it shows that H1, namely Consumer Behavior, has a positive and significant influence on the Purchasing Decisions of Shabbypinkstore Consumers in Medan City, which is acceptable. the count is obtained with a value of 3.713, which means that the count value is $3.713 > \text{table } 1.984$ and the p-value in the sig column is $0.000 < 0.05$, which means it has a significant effect. This explains that consumer behavior has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for Shabbypinkstore consumers in Medan City.

b. The Influence of Digital Marketing on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the results of research that has been carried out, it shows that H1, namely (Digital Marketing), has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for Shabbypinkstore consumers in Medan City. the count is obtained with a value of 3.713, which means that the count value is $3.713 > \text{table } 1.985$ and the p-value in the sig column is $0.000 < 0.05$ which means it has a significant effect. This explains that (Digital Marketing) has a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for Shabbypinkstore consumers in Medan City.

c. The Influence of Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing on Purchasing Decisions

Based on the results of research that has been carried out, it shows that Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions of Shabbypinkstore Consumers in Medan City, it was found that the value of Fcount (150.083) $> F\text{table } (3.09)$ and Sig. equal to $0.000 < 0.05$. So, it can be concluded that this shows that the Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing variables together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions for Shabbypinkstore consumers in Medan City.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

After the results of this research have been analyzed and presented, in this chapter the author can draw conclusions which are the essence of the research that has been carried out as follows:

1. The research results show that judging from the t value of $6.461 > 1.985$, this shows that Consumer Behavior has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions, if Consumer Behavior increases, Purchasing Decisions will be higher for Shabbypinkstore Consumers in Medan City.
2. The research results show that in Persia with a calculated t value of $3.713 > 1.985$. This shows that Digital Marketing has a positive and significant influence on Purchasing Decisions. The higher the Digital Marketing

created by the Shabbypinkstore store, the higher the purchasing level among Shabbypinkstore Consumers in Medan City.

3. The research results show that together (simultaneously) the f value is 150.083. This shows that simultaneously the variables have a positive and significant influence on purchasing decisions for Shabbypinkstore consumers in Medan.

Based on the research results that have been obtained, the author provides several suggestions, namely as follows:

1. Consumers are advised to consider the results of this research as a reference in making use of services in illustrating that in purchasing decisions there are internal and external factors that influence.
2. For future researchers, they can clarify the sample criteria and take samples from communities that meet these criteria.
3. It is hoped that this research will be a useful reference for conducting further research related to the Influence of Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing on Purchasing Decisions among Shabbypinkstore consumers in Medan City.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations, so further research needs to be carried out regarding the topic "The Influence of Consumer Behavior and Digital Marketing-Based Marketing Mix on Purchasing Decisions" to provide additional information to readers.

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